

A VIBRATION-BASED STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM FOR GFRP LAMINATE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Structural health monitoring is being considered to detect minor damage prior to being combined and propagated to cause failure to composite structures. Composite plates made of glass fibre pre-preg and cured out-of-autoclave used in this study. A pre-defined delamination in forms of polytetrafluoroethylene was inserted between the plies during the lamination process. The effects of the delamination length on modal characteristics of the composite plates were investigated. The effect of the composite plate size on damage detection and location was also studied. A random vibration wave was used to excite the composite structure. A piezoelectric sensor, polyvinylidene fluoride, was used to capture the response of the system. Response signals were processed using an in-house built high-level estimation algorithm. It was found that damage caused a frequency shift, the amount of shift depends on the delamination length. Mode natural frequencies showed different response to the delamination.

1 INTRODUCTION

Damage in composite materials may be caused by external loads, i.e. a bird hits a wind turbine blade accidentally, or by operational conditions, such as fatigue [1], [2]. Composite laminates may suffer from different types of damage, such as matrix cracks, delamination, and/or fiber rupture [3]. Delamination initiates and grows under low amounts of loads [4], [5]. The delamination is invisible damage since it grows between plies and therefore represents an obstacle for large number of composite laminate structures. The delamination causes a significant reduction in mechanical properties of composite laminates, especially compression after impact properties, as it encourages plies to act independently [6]. It is highly desirable to develop a monitoring system that detects delamination at an early stage in order to avoid a catastrophic failure of composite structures [7]. Delamination initiation and growth depends on many factors, such as fiber type, weave types, stitching, matrix properties and stacking sequence [8]. Therefore, a monitoring system that addresses these challenges is desirable.

Structural health monitoring of a composite structure is directly linked to its performance; therefore, it is a major factor in the economical and safety operations [9]. A reliable, effective and efficient damage monitoring system is highly desirable in many applications, such as aerospace, automotive and energy sectors [10], [11]. The response of composite structures to excitation is complex [12]. Composite laminates are made of three main components that are reinforcing element (fibers), bonding element (matrix) and an interphase region between fibers and matrix. The way composite laminates deform and fail depends on these three components. Damage of interest determines the type of excitation required, for instance delamination cause a small degradation in tensile properties of composite, however, it causes a significant reduction in shear and compression after impact properties.

Few structural health monitoring systems have been proposed in literature, such as acoustic, thermography, fiber optics, and vibration-based structural health monitoring [13], [14]. Acoustic can be divided into two types that are ultrasonic and sonic techniques [15]. In ultrasonic techniques the ultrasonic pulse in an object is reflected when it hits an interface between two regions that have different acoustic impedance. Sonic techniques rely on the fact that when damage is initiated that is a combined by sound emission, those sounds can be collected and analyzed and damage can be detected and located [16]. This technique requires a dedicated digital signal processor with an analogue-to-digital converter for each probe. Fiber optics structural health monitoring has been studied extensively to monitor strain and detect damage [17]. The main limitations of fiber optics are the signal acquired is complex in nature and requires a sophisticated signal processing technique for analysis. Fiber optics may cause resin rich areas and local deformation, they are also brittle which can break under loading and before the composite fails.

Vibration-based structural health monitoring systems are compelling techniques since they monitor the behavior of the whole structure, i.e. fibers, matrix and interface [18]. Vibration-based structural health monitoring systems rely on an excitation signal at frequency > 2 kHz. Excitation signals may vary, they can be deterministic or random [19]. All environmental vibration waves are random; therefore, this paper presented a comprehensive vibration-based structural health monitoring system (SHM), the system was aimed at woven fabric glass fiber reinforced laminate structures. The composite structure was excited using a random vibration wave. The effect of the delamination length and panel size on the natural frequencies and damage detectability and locatibility were investigated.

2 METHODOLOGY

Composite laminate plates were made of a 2 x 2mm twill weave glass fibre (GF) prepreg VTC 401-G290T (SHD Composite Materials, UK). This was cut into sheets and hand laid onto a glass plate. A polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) interply was inserted at a selected location in the layup stack during the layup process to produce controlled delamination. Different composite laminate sizes and three interply delamination sizes (400 mm^2 , 1000 mm^2 , and 2400 mm^2) were investigated. Then the panels were cured in an oven according to the manufacturer recommendations. To establish a relationship between various parameters, such as delamination length, location, and composite plate size and frequency responses of structures, design of experiments (DOE) using response surface method (RSM) was adopted. The composite plates were excited using environmental vibration data at a frequency band of 500 Hz as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Representative vibration data used to excite the glass fiber composite laminates. The data was collected from CGJ aircraft.

The composite plate was installed on an electrodynamic shaker (LDS 406, Bruel & Kajer, Denmark), the electrodynamic shaker was driven by a wave generator 33210A (Keysight, UK) and the

random vibration wave was provided to the wave generator via a waveform editor as shown in Figure 2. The response of the composite plate to the excitation signal was collected via an oscilloscope DSOX-2004A (Agilent Technologies, USA) at acquisition rate of 2500 S/s.

Figure 2: Experimental set up for the measurements of frequency responses.

The composite plate vibration response was collected via piezoelectric sensors (polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF)) that were attached onto the surface of the composite laminate plates. The locations of the sensors were chosen where high strain occurred, those locations were selected depending on finite element simulations as shown in Figure 3. The vibration data of the composite plate was normalised, the unwanted temporal relationships were removed from the data by using trend removal filter in MATLAB. Outliers were removed using a standard classical method, and then the data was averaged using a local averaging technique. The data was then smoothed using a Savitzky - Golay filter. This filter uses a convolution process, which adopts a linear least square method, to smooth the signal without disrupting the original signal tendency. Features were extracted, reduced, and selected to detect and locate damage. A dedicated algorithm based on Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) was built to perform the analysis. It is important to note that there are many variables could potentially cause frequency shift. Those variables are mass, damping and panel dimensions, therefore, it is important to normalise the data prior to data analysis. The data were normalised using the following formulas to eliminate the effect of the mass and damping respectively.

Figure 3: An array of sensors that were distributed over a GFRP plate to detect and locate the damage. Different sizes of delamination were used those being 400, 1000, and 2400 mm².

$$w_n = w_m \sqrt{\frac{1}{1 - \frac{m_i - m_o}{m_o}}} \quad (1)$$

Where w_n is the normalized natural frequency, w_m is the measured natural frequency, m_i is the damaged panel mass (g), m_o is the healthy panel mass (g)

$$w_n = w_m \sqrt{(1 - \xi^2)} \quad (2)$$

Where ξ is the damping ratio of the healthy panel.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Gaussian model was used to analyze the frequency responses as shown in Figure 4. It was found that the sensitivity of frequency modes to delamination presence were different. It can be seen in Figure 4 that due to interply delamination cracks the natural frequency increased by up to 4.2 %. The frequency response of a healthy panel was found to be 409.63 Hz, however, when 2400 mm² interply delamination crack (D2400) was inserted the frequency increased to 425 Hz. The increase in frequency implies that the PTFE insert dynamic characteristics of the glass fiber laminate.

Figure 4: Resonant frequencies shift due to delamination occurrence.

To investigate this issue further a smaller interply delamination crack of 1000 mm² (D1000) was inserted, it was found that the frequency deviated from 409.63 Hz for healthy panel to 418.56 Hz which confirms that the dynamics of the plate was enhanced due to insertion of PTFE. To investigate the sensitivity of the SHM system to delamination size a 400 mm² (D400) interply delamination crack was inserted; it was found that the frequency increased by up to 410.51 Hz. It was concluded that when the interply delamination size increases the frequency shift increases as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The effect of delamination length on natural frequencies of 200 x 200 mm glass fibre composite panel.

It was also found that the location of the interply delamination crack in the laminate is critical. In symmetric laminate the closer the delamination to the neutral axis the less variations in natural frequencies occurred. This is attributed to the lower strain variation in the planes close to the neutral

axis. Also, the higher the distance between the PVDF sensor and the delamination the less variations in frequencies occurred as shown in Figure 6. This is attributed to signal-to-noise ratio, the more distant the sensor was the lower signal-to-noise ratio was.

It can be seen in Figure 6 that the panel 300 x 300 mm has achieved the highest variations in the natural frequency, that was due to high strain generated in the panel during the vibration tests. On the other hand, 400 x 400 panel showed the lowest change in natural frequencies that can be attributed to the high distance between the sensor and the delamination location.

Figure 6: Percentage shifts of natural frequencies (κ) due to damage occurrence at various distances from the damage area.

9 CONCLUSIONS

Vibration-based structural health monitoring system is a universal system that detects, locates damage as well as predicts the remaining life of a structure based on changes in natural frequencies of a composite structure. The changes in natural frequencies can be related to change in mechanical properties of the composites and consequently the remaining life of the composite can be predicted. The amount of change in natural frequencies depend on many factors, such as delamination size to panel size, and delamination length at a fixed panel size. The through-thickness location of delamination plays an important role in damage detection procedure. When the excitation signal of a deflection nature, such as vibration, the closer the delamination to the neural axis the less detectable the damage is, this phenomenon becomes more obvious when a piezoelectric sensor was used.

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